

The effect on leaffolder damage of different methods of applying nitrogen was investigated further in a split-plot design with two nitrogen levels (main treatment) and seven methods of application (subtreatments). In some treatments N as urea was applied to the root zone

with an applicator or by hand in paper balls. Fenitrothion (0.05%) was sprayed at 40 DT, and fenthion (0.05%) at 55 DT. Leaffolder infestation was assessed by recording the percentage of damaged leaves at 60 DT when the pest occurrence was highest.

Applying all the N basally tended to increase the leaffolder damage level above that with use of other methods (see table). But at a moderate N level, the application method appeared to have little effect on leaffolder damage. ■

Pest management and control WEEDS

Propagation of perennial paddy weeds in unplanted paddy fields

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Recent agricultural policy on surplus rice in Japan increased the unplanted paddy fields all over the country. Perennial paddy weeds proliferated in such fields and their propagules were spread by plowing and puddling. This seems to be one reason for the recent rapid increase of perennial paddy weeds.

To determine the propagation ability of a single plant in unplanted paddy fields, an experiment used five serious perennial paddy weeds: *Sagittaria pygmaea* Miq. (Sp), *Cyperus serotinus* Rottb. (Cs), *Eleocharis kuroguwai* Ohwi (Ek), *Scirpus planiculmis* Fr. Schm. (Spl), and *Potamogeton distinctus* A. Benn. (Pd). The field was plowed and puddled after a uniform application of 50 kg N/ha, 100 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 100 kg K₂O/ha. One plant of each weed was transplanted in the center of a 9-m² plot separately on 10 June 1981. Hand weeding was carried out to avoid the effect of other weeds. The number of plants, the occupied land area, and the plant den-

Distribution map of perennial paddy weeds propagated from a single plant. Niigata, Japan, 1980.

Propagation from a single plant of perennial paddy weeds in an unplanted paddy field. Niigata, Japan, 1980.

Weed species	Plants ^a (no.)	Occupied land area ^a (m ²)	Density ^a (plants/m ²)	Propagules ^b	
				No.	Fresh wt (g)
<i>Sagittaria pygmaea</i>	313	0.939	333.3	822	41.1
<i>Cyperus serotinus</i>	321	1.551	210.8	794	190.0
<i>Eleocharis kuroguwai</i>	51	0.793	71.9	51	68.2
<i>Scirpus planiculmis</i>	214	3.494	61.2	1,244	1295.9
<i>Potamogeton distinctus</i>	457	2.615	174.8	118	24.7

^aExamined on 5 August 1980. ^bExamined on 12 November 1980.

sity were examined on 5 August and the propagules formed were examined on 12 November.

The results are shown in the figure and the table. Considerable propagules

were formed even in the least propagated weed. The results suggest that a few weeds remaining in the unplanted part of a paddy field is a big source of propagules for the following year. ■

Efficiency of fluchloralin, butachlor, nitrofen, and hand weeding for rice weed control

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A field experiment at the Agricultural College Farm (Palli Siksha Sadana),

Sriniketan, Visva-Bharati, West Bengal during 1979 kharif studied the comparative efficiency of some granular herbicides and hand weeding for controlling weeds in the semihumid lateritic tract of the state. There were 12 weed species: 3 were grasses, 3 were sedges, and 6 were broadleaved of which *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, and *Ludwigia perennis*

were predominant in the experimental field. The granular herbicides fluchloralin at 2.0 kg a.i./ha 7 days after transplanting (DT), nitrofen 1.5 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT, and butachlor at 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT reduced the weed population but showed no injurious effect on the crop (see table). Nitrofen and butachlor gave very promising results in